

DEVELOPING A FRAMEWORK FOR EVALUATING LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN MIDDLE SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Annotation.** In this article, the author describes the importance of lexical competence, the reasons why lexical competence is evaluated, and effective ways of forming a framework to evaluate vocabulary knowledge of middle school learners, since lexical competence is highly valued by teachers and students themselves*

***Key words.** Vocabulary, assessment procedures, game-based tasks, rewarding, communication.*

Introduction. Lexical competence is that aspect of communicative competence that deals with knowledge of lexical or vocabulary items and their meaning and the ability to use them appropriately. It is generally well-known that without grammatical accuracy an utterance may be understood, but without precise vocabulary it is indeed difficult. Therefore, lexical competence is highlighted in middle school settings to increase pupils' awareness of a significant role lexical competence plays in language learning.

There exist several questions, such as why we need to assess lexical competence among middle school learners? Firstly, not only in schools, but also in kindergartens, children put initial steps towards language learning experiences. Teachers applying modern teaching methods and techniques work on children's vocabulary knowledge rather than making them overwhelmed with obtaining confusing grammar structures. For the reason, it is a real mistake to commence instruction from a theoretical part, since in this period those children have a short attention span. It means that they get bored, exhausted faster than adult learners physically and mentally. Since they develop vocabulary basis from early stages of

education, this knowledge must be under control of teacher to avoid misunderstanding and misuse in communication and formal cases.

Furthermore, these days, teaching and learning took another form that differs immensely from the previous ones. To be more precise, communicative language teaching (CLT) method is dominant as a up-to-date way of teaching. This method is applied in assessment procedures of lexical competence among middle schoolers. Before assessment days, instructors are required to be skillful at making a thorough plan of how to evaluate lexical abilities of students. There are several factors that must be taken into consideration while preparing assessment tasks, including:

- Choose an appropriate material suitable for pupils' level
- Create authentic material so as to engage learners in assessments
- Allocate adequate time to complete the task
- Apply games and fun activities while evaluating
- Divide students into pairs and groups to work together by helping and support each other
- Prepare rewards to motivate to continue learning.

Conclusion. Since lexical competence is highly valued by instructors and linguists in middle school education, it must be assessed, analyzed through well-prepared procedures mentioned above. The reason for that, even a tiny mistake in assessment can make a learner disappointed from his performance and learning resulting in less enthusiasm to go on for learning. To avoid all problems given above, instructors are highly recommended to create a framework for they themselves by following abovementioned accurate procedures on a regular basis.

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